

Met Office Projecting Future Sea Level (ProFSea) tool - User Guide

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Abbreviations

AR5	IPCC's 5 th Assessment Report
AR6	IPCC's 6 th Assessment Report
CMIP5	Coupled Model Intercomparison Project Phase 5
GIA	Glacial Isostatic Adjustment
GMSL	Global-mean sea Level
GMST	Global Mean Surface Temperature
GRD	Gravity, Rotation and Solid-Earth Deformation
GTE	Global Thermal Expansion
IPCC	Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change
MSL	Mean Sea Level
NERC	Natural Environment Research Council
ProFSea	Projecting Future Sea Level
PSMSL	Permanent Service for Mean Sea Level
RCP	Representative Concentration Pathway
SPF	Strategic Priorities Fund
SSH	Sea Surface Height
UKCP18	UK Climate Projections 2018
UKCR	UK Climate Resilience
UKRI	UK Research and Innovation

Definitions

Barystatic sea level – “The part of global-mean sea-level change which is due to the addition to the ocean of water mass that formerly resided within the land area (as land water storage or land ice) or in the atmosphere (which contains a relatively tiny mass of water), or (if negative) the removal of mass from the ocean to be stored elsewhere. It is also called barystatic sea-level change” (Gregory et al., 2019).

Geoid - the shape that the ocean surface would take under the influence of the gravity of Earth, including gravitational attraction and Earth's rotation, if other influences such as winds and tides were absent.

Glacial isostatic adjustment – “Ongoing changes in the solid-Earth caused by past changes in land ice” (Gregory et al., 2019).

GRD estimates – “Changes in the Earth’s Gravity, Rotation (and hence centrifugal acceleration) and viscoelastic solid-Earth Deformation” (Gregory et al., 2019).

Groundwater extraction - The extraction of groundwater, pumped from underground aquifers, as a source of freshwater. In many aquifers the groundwater must be pumped out through boreholes or wells.

Impoundment - A body of water (such as a reservoir) that is confined by a barrier such as a dam or floodgate.

Monte Carlo - A method that makes random draws from an underlying distribution many times to build up a picture of the combined uncertainties.

Sterodynamic sea level – “Relative sea-level change due to changes in ocean density and circulation, with inverse barometer correction” (Gregory et al., 2019).

Contributors

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1. Introduction

The UK Climate Resilience (UKCR) Programme is a four-year Strategic Priorities Fund (SPF) scientific research programme led jointly by UK Research and Innovation (UKRI) and the Met Office with Natural Environment Research Council (NERC). Under the UKCR Programme, the Climate Service Pilot: Improving Coastal Resilience¹ project, the Met Office Projecting Future Sea Level (ProFSea) tool was developed. This is an interactive tool to provide local sea-level projections at user defined locations across the globe. This document summarises the underpinning science on sea-level projections and provides guidance on how to set-up and run the ProFSea tool. It is recommended that you read this document before using the ProFSea tool as it describes the data requirements, the main outputs as well as the caveats and limitations.

In addition to this user guide, we recommend that you read the UK Climate Projections 2018 (UKCP18) Marine Report (Palmer et al., 2018) and Palmer et al. (2020), for a comprehensive description of the underpinning science, detailed methods including the consideration of changes in surges, tides, and coastal waves, and a synthesis of the results for the 21st century.

The ProFSea tool provides future projections of global and local sea level based on the methods described in the Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change's (IPCC) Fifth Assessment Report (AR5; Church et al., 2013) which are rooted in climate model simulations carried out as part of the Coupled Model Intercomparison Project Phase 5 (CMIP5; Taylor et al., 2012). The emission scenarios are based on Representative Concentration Pathways (RCPs) and further information on these are available on the UKCP18 website². The projections consist of annual sea-level change relative to a baseline period; they are provided for 2007-2100 for the three future emissions scenarios (RCP2.6, RCP4.5 and RCP8.5) and are available for nine percentiles (5th, 10th, 30th, 33rd, 50th, 67th, 70th, 90th and 95th). Note the ProFSea tool does not provide projections for local sea level extremes, which are considered a combination of the tides, waves, and surge. Several extensions to the IPCC AR5 methodology have been applied.

1. The inclusion of scenario-dependant projections of mass addition from Antarctic ice discharge developed by Levermann et al. (2014).
2. Local projections of steric sea-level change were scaled to better isolate the forced response from internal variability (e.g., Bilbao et al., 2015).
3. The IPCC AR5 Monte Carlo methodology for global-mean sea-level (GMSL) projections was extended for the local sea-level projections, this preserves the

¹ [Climate Service Pilot: Improving Coastal Resilience - \(ukclimateresilience.org\)](https://ukclimateresilience.org)

² [UKCP18 Guidance - Representative Concentration Pathways.pdf \(metoffice.gov.uk\)](https://www.metoffice.gov.uk/ukcp18/guidance-representative-concentration-pathways.pdf)

correlations between the different sea-level uncertainties and allows for traceability.

4. A more comprehensive treatment of uncertainty was developed. Several different estimates of sea-level change associated with glacial isostatic adjustment (GIA) were included, as well as several estimates for the barystatic-GRD fingerprints (Gravity, Rotation, Deformation; the spatial patterns of sea-level change, defined in Section 2.2.1).

The ProFSea tool can be used to generate and assess the impact of sea-level projections in different regions around the world. It is anticipated that these sea-level projections can be used within the development of climate services, which can support communities, public, private and third sector organisations in their understanding of how sea level could change in the future. Ultimately helping society to make informed decisions about future climate risk to be better prepared, stay safe and thrive.

The main sections of this document are underpinning science, methods, setting up the tool and running the tool.

2. Underpinning science

2.1. Global-mean sea level

Changes in global and local sea level arise from a wide variety of geophysical processes that operate on different temporal and spatial scales. GMSL change occurs from changes in ocean density, glaciers, ice sheets, and land water storage. Globally, ocean density is dominated by thermal expansion, i.e., the tendency for seawater to expand and become less dense as temperature increases. Freshwater input to the ocean arises from loss of land-based ice from mountain glaciers and the melting of the Greenland and Antarctic ice sheets. Finally, changes in land water storage, through processes such as groundwater extraction and reservoir impoundment, make a substantial contribution to GMSL change.

2.2. Local sea level

For most coastal locations, local sea-level projections over the 21st century will be within $\pm 20\%$ of the median GMSL projection (Fox-Kemper et al., 2021). Regional mean sea-level (MSL) change occurs from changes in ocean circulation and density, land-based ice and water storage and GIA.

- Changes in temperature and salinity are important factors affecting the regional ocean circulation and/or seawater density which in turn leave their imprint in the shape of the sea surface. Changes in ocean circulation and seawater density vary markedly among climate models and are therefore highly uncertain. This is accounted for in the local

sterodynamic component of sea-level change (discussed in Table 3-1).

- Changes in land-based ice and water storage result in spatial patterns of local sea-level change through the associated impact of mass redistribution on the Earth's gravity field and other effects (discussed in Section 2.2.1).
- GIA refers to the ongoing response of the Earth's mantle to the last deglaciation and gives rise to a spatial pattern of sea-level change (discussed in Section 2.2.2). While vertical land is the dominant contribution to this pattern, gravitational and rotational effects also make a substantive contribution (Shennan et al., 2012).

The superposition of the three different spatial elements described above, determine the sea-level change for a given location.

2.2.1. Gravity, Rotation, solid-Earth Deformation

Changes in the amount of land-based ice and water storage induce spatial patterns of local MSL change as a result of changes to the Earth's gravity, rotation, and solid-Earth deformation. Gregory et al. (2019) refers to these effects collectively as GRD (Gravity, Rotation, Deformation). The GRD estimates for each of the barystatic components: (i) Antarctic surface mass balance, (ii) Antarctic ice dynamics, (iii) Greenland surface mass balance, (iv) Greenland ice dynamics, (v) worldwide glaciers, and (vi) changes in land water storage, are expressed as the local MSL change per unit of GMSL rise. An example of these spatial patterns, along with their associated standard deviation are shown in Figure 2-1 (for UK specific patterns see Figure A 1).

Depending on the geographic location, the spatial patterns of GRD estimates can have an important impact on local MSL projections; the components of GMSL change can be attenuated or intensified. The addition of fresh water from the Antarctic and Greenland ice sheets (Figure 2-1, a and g), as well as the ice dynamics components (Figure 2-1, b and h), give rise to a near-field decrease and a far-field increase in mass change. The spatial patterns of GRD estimates associated with worldwide glaciers and land water storage are more complex, due to their mass distributions being more geographically widespread (Figure 2-1, c and i).

Figure 2-1: Estimates of the combined effect of mass changes on Earth's gravity, rotation, and solid-Earth deformation (GRD) on local relative sea level. Panels (a), (b), (c), (g) and (h) show the mean of three sets of estimates with corresponding standard deviations across estimates shown in (d), (e), (f), (j) and (k). Only a single estimate was available for land water, and therefore, no standard deviation is shown. GRD estimates are expressed as the ratio of local MSL to GMSL per unit rise/fall with the 1:1 and zero contours indicated by the solid and dotted grey lines, respectively. Reproduced from: Palmer et al. (2020).

2.2.2. Glacial Isostatic Adjustment

As with the GRD estimates, ongoing GIA also results in a spatial pattern of MSL change. GIA is the very slow ongoing movement of the land due to the removal of ice-age glaciers since the last glaciation. While a significant effect from GIA is on the upward and downward vertical land motion, there is also a contribution from changes in the mass redistribution which impacts the Earth's rotation and gravity field, subsequently affecting the local MSL. It is well known that GIA leads to substantial spatial variations in the rates of MSL change. An example of these spatial patterns is shown in Figure 2-2 (for UK specific patterns see Figure A 2).

During the last glaciation regions of large ice mass changes were North America, the Arctic, and Antarctica. These areas correspond with positive values of sea-level change along their adjacent coastal areas (indicating sea-level rise relative to the land). Although note that these

areas are also associated with the largest overall spread in GIA estimates, based on the standard deviation (not shown).

For the sea-level projections produced by the ProFSea tool, in the UK the GIA estimate is based on the 15-member ensemble used in UKCP18 (Palmer et al., 2018), elsewhere this is based on two estimates, the ICE-5G model (Peltier, 2004), and the Australian National University update of Nakada and Lambeck (1988) in 2004 - 2005 (Slangen et al., 2014). The differences between the two methods are highlighted in Table 3-1.

Figure 2-2: Estimates of the effect of glacial isostatic adjustment (GIA) on sea-level change based on ICE-5G model (Peltier, 2004), and the Australian National University update of Nakada and Lambeck (1988) in 2004–2005 (Slangen et al., 2014). The zero line is indicated by the dotted contours. The standard deviation of the three GIA estimates is shown in (d). Units for all panels are mm yr^{-1} . Adapted from: Palmer et al. (2020).

2.3. Local sea level extremes

At local scales, the impacts of coastal sea-level change primarily arise from extreme water level events. It is well known that many of the worst and earliest effects of sea-level rise will be experienced during extreme high-water events, which are usually associated with high tides combined with storm surges and may involve overtopping due to extreme wave heights. While

previous studies (e.g. Lowe et al., 2009; Howard et al., 2014; Cannaby et al., 2016) have emphasised the dominance of time-mean sea-level change in driving variations in future coastal sea-level extremes, it is important to also consider changes in the extremes themselves that may arise through, for example, changes in atmospheric storminess.

The various components that lead to global-mean sea-level rise, regional sea-level change and local sea level extremes are shown in the schematic in Figure 2-3 and each of these terms are discussed in more detail in Section 2.1 of the UKCP18 Marine Report (Palmer et al., 2018).

Figure 2-3: Schematic to summarise the various contributions to global-mean sea-level rise (left-hand column); regional sea-level change (middle column); and local sea-level extremes (right-hand column). The potential interaction between local time-mean sea level and tide and surge characteristics is indicated by the black dashed lines. The grey text highlights some of the non-climatic processes that can give rise to sea-level change through vertical land motion. The processes highlighted within the red box are those that are represented within the ProFSea tool. Adapted from: UKCP18 Marine Report (Palmer et al., 2018).

3. Methods

3.1. Global-mean sea-level projections

The GMSL projections are based on the methods described in the IPCC AR5 (Church et al., 2013) which are rooted in climate model simulations carried out as part of the CMIP5 (Taylor et al., 2012). These projections are underpinned by 21 CMIP5 climate model simulations of global thermal expansion (GTE) and global-mean surface temperature (GMST). All the projections presented in this report and produced by the ProFSea tool are premised on the RCP climate change scenarios described by Meinshausen et al. (2011). Following IPCC AR5, the ranges of the time-mean sea-level projections produced are within the 5th and 95th

percentiles of the underlying model simulations, for a given RCP scenario. It should be noted that there may be a greater than 10% chance that the real-world response lies outside these ranges and this likelihood cannot be accurately quantified. We cannot rule out substantial additional sea-level rise associated with accelerated ice sheet mass loss (Fox-Kemper et al., 2021), for example through dynamic ice discharge from the West Antarctic Ice Sheet (see Section 3.2.1 of UKCP18 Marine Report (Palmer et al., 2018)).

3.1.1. Global Monte Carlo

Following IPCC AR5, a 450,000-member Monte Carlo simulation is produced for each RCP scenario that forms the basis of both the GMSL (Figure 3-1) and local MSL projections (Figure 3-2). GMSL projections of thermal expansion were taken directly from the 21 CMIP5 climate model simulations using annual mean GTE as an input. The mean and standard deviation of the time series of global thermal expansion (relative to a 1986-2005 baseline) were used to generate a Monte Carlo distribution of 450 thousand sets of sea-level projections, assuming a normal distribution, see process (1) in Figure 3-1.

GMST change was used to estimate the response of glaciers and Greenland and Antarctic surface mass balance terms using established parameterisation schemes. As with GTE, the mean and standard deviation of the time series of global surface temperature change (relative to a 1986-2005 baseline) were used to generate a Monte Carlo distribution of 450 thousand sets of sea-level projections, assuming a normal distribution, see process (1) in Figure 3-1.

To account for methodological uncertainty in the parameterization schemes, 1000 random samples are taken from each scheme, which are combined with the 450 samples of GTE and GMST to generate the full Monte Carlo distribution of 450 thousand sets of sea-level projections ($450 \times 1,000 = 450,000$ members). The parameterization schemes for the barystatic components are based on global and regional models, and observations, which are explained by IPCC AR5 (Church et al., 2013) and Palmer et al. (2020).

Figure 3-1: Flowchart of the Monte Carlo method of IPCC AR5 (Church et al., 2013) for producing global-mean sea level (GMSL) projections. Where global thermal expansion (GTE) timeseries relative to a 1986-2005 baseline is used directly to generate the global-mean sea level (GMSL) projections of thermal expansion. Where global surface air temperature (GSAT, referred in the text above as global-mean surface temperature (GMST)) change was used to estimate the response of glaciers and Greenland and Antarctic surface mass balance terms using established parameterisation schemes. Reproduced from: Hermans et al. (2021), Supporting Information, Text S1.

3.2. Local sea-level projections

The local sea-level projections are derived from the GMSL projections, taking account of several additional processes (detailed in Table 3-1). First, the spatial patterns of MSL change associated with each of the barystatic GMSL contributions (the addition of mass from land-based ice or water storage) are incorporated using estimates of the effects on Earth's gravity, rotation, and solid-Earth deformation (GRD fingerprints; Gregory et al., 2019). The effects of local changes in ocean density and circulation are included by establishing regression relationships between global thermal expansion and local steric sea-level change (the increase in the water column due to density changes), an example of this is shown in Figure 5-2). Finally, the spatial pattern of local MSL change from the response of the solid-Earth to the last de-glaciation (often referred to as GIA) is included.

3.2.1. Regional Monte Carlo

The Monte Carlo simulations for the local MSL projections, randomly selects a single case from the 450,000-member Monte Carlo of GMSL projections. Each case includes a timeseries of the steric and barystatic GMSL components, which preserves any underlying correlations between them (grey arrow in Figure 3-2). The timeseries of global thermal expansion is combined with a randomly drawn regression coefficient from the 21 CMIP5 climate model simulations, to estimate the steric sea-level change at a given location (red arrow in Figure 3-2). Each of the barystatic timeseries (with the exception of land water), is combined with a randomly selected GRD estimate from the same model (green arrow in Figure 3-2). A single GRD estimate is available for the land water component (Slangen et al., 2014), which is also combined with the corresponding timeseries. The resulting seven timeseries of local MSL change are then combined with a randomly selected estimate of GIA (blue arrow in Figure 3-2). In the UK the GIA estimate is based on the 15-member ensemble used in UKCP18 (Palmer et al., 2018), elsewhere this is based on two estimates, the ICE-5G model (Peltier, 2004), and the Australian National University update of Nakada and Lambeck (1988) in 2004 - 2005 (Slangen et al., 2014). The differences between the two methods are highlighted in Table 3-1.

This process is repeated 100,000 times for each location to build a distribution of MSL projections, for each RCP scenario. Following IPCC AR5, the 5th and 95th percentiles of this distribution indicate the spread in the total MSL change and for each of the individual components.

Figure 3-2: A schematic representation of the Monte Carlo simulation performed for the regional mean sea level (MSL) projections. The above process is repeated 100,000 times to build up a distribution of sea-level projections for each location for each RCP scenario. Reproduced from: Palmer et al. (2020).

3.3. Other scenarios

The local MSL projections produced by the ProFSea tool correspond to the IPCC AR5 “likely range”, as determined by their expert judgement. IPCC AR5 interpreted the 5th to 95th percentiles as having a “2/3 chance” of spanning the real-world sea-level rise for any given RCP scenario (Church et al., 2013). As noted above, we cannot rule out substantial additional sea-level rise associated primarily with dynamic ice discharge from the West Antarctic Ice Sheet. The IPCC’s 6th Assessment Report (AR6; Fox-Kemper et al., 2021) provides local sea-level projections based on a low-likelihood high-impact storyline of accelerated ice sheet mass loss to 2150 that can be used alongside the projections produced here.

UKCP18 also developed extended exploratory time-mean sea-level projections out to 2300 which have much lower confidence than the 21st Century projections. They are designed to be used alongside the 21st Century projections for those interested in exploring post-2100 changes. These projections can be considered as sensitivity studies and should not be interpreted as showing the full range of post-2100 behaviour, or the most likely behaviour. The potential for additional sea-level rise from Antarctic dynamic ice discharge is even more uncertain on these time horizons, with some studies suggesting several additional metres of sea-level rise by 2300 under emissions scenario RCP8.5.

IPCC AR6 states that in the longer term, “sea level is committed to rise for centuries to millennia”. The amount to which sea level will rise is dependent upon future temperature rise. If global temperature rise is limited to 1.5°C of warming, global-mean sea level will rise by approximately 2-3m. However, if global temperature rise reaches 5°C of warming, global-mean sea-level rise could be 19-22m (*low confidence*), see section B.5 of the Summary for Policymakers. In: Climate Change 2021: The Physical Science Basis (IPCC, 2021).

We recommend that decision makers make use of the sea-level projections produced by the ProFSea tool alongside multiple strands of evidence, including H++ scenarios (Palmer et al., 2018)³ or the low-likelihood, high-impact storyline presented in AR6 (Fox-Kemper et al., 2021), when assessing vulnerabilities to future extreme water levels.

³ “High-plus-plus” or “H++” scenarios are designed to explore the high-end plausible future sea-level rise and complement the process-based sea-level projections presented in IPCC assessments.

Table 3-1: Summary of the local sea level components and associated methods. Within the UK sea-level projections are based on the methods described in the UKCP18 Marine Report (Palmer et al., 2018) whereas for all other locations globally these are based on methods described in Palmer et al (2020).

Sea level component	UK - UKCP18 method (Palmer et al., 2018)	Global - Palmer et al. (2020)
i) Ocean sterodynamic	Regression slopes between global thermal expansion and local sterodynamic sea-level change are computed for all mainland UK coastal locations, for each CMIP5 model (on the model's native grid). Each value is assigned a probability weighting to ensure equal sampling across the models in the Monte Carlo step.	Regression slopes between global thermal expansion and local sterodynamic sea-level change are computed for each location, for each CMIP5 model (on the model's native grid).
ii) Glaciers	AR5 timeseries of mass addition from glaciers are combined with the corresponding mass fingerprint, which is drawn at random from two independent model estimates (Slangen et al., 2014; Spada and Stocchi, 2007). Linear interpolation is used to extract the local fingerprint value at each coastal grid point.	The methods are identical to UKCP18 with the exception that three GRD fingerprints are drawn from the Monte Carlo rather than two.
iii) Greenland – surface mass balance	AR5 timeseries of mass addition from surface mass balance are combined with the corresponding mass fingerprint, which is drawn at random from two independent model estimates (as above). Linear interpolation is used to extract the local fingerprint value at each coastal grid point.	The methods are identical to UKCP18 with the exception that three GRD fingerprints are drawn from the Monte Carlo rather than two.
iv) Antarctica – surface mass balance	AR5 timeseries of mass addition from surface mass balance are combined with the corresponding mass fingerprint, which is drawn at random from two independent model estimates (as above). Linear interpolation is used to extract the local fingerprint value at each coastal grid point.	The methods are identical to UKCP18 with the exception that three GRD fingerprints are drawn from the Monte Carlo rather than two.
v) Greenland – ice dynamics	AR5 timeseries of mass addition from ice dynamics are combined with the corresponding mass fingerprint, which is drawn at random from two independent model estimates (as	The methods are identical to UKCP18 with the exception that three GRD fingerprints are drawn from the Monte Carlo rather than two.

	above). Linear interpolation is used to extract the local fingerprint value at each coastal grid point.	
vi) Antarctica – ice dynamics	Levermann et al. (2014) timeseries of mass addition from ice dynamics are combined with the corresponding mass fingerprint, which is drawn at random from two independent model estimates (as above). Linear interpolation is used to extract the local fingerprint value at each coastal grid point.	The methods are identical to UKCP18 with the exception that three GRD fingerprints are drawn from the Monte Carlo rather than two.
vii) Land water	AR5 timeseries of mass addition is combined with a single estimate of the mass fingerprint from Slangen et al. (2014).	The methods are identical to UKCP18.
viii) Glacial isostatic adjustment (GIA)	A 15-member ensemble of the total effect of GIA on local sea level is provided by the BRITICE_CHRONO project (Bradley, pers. comm.). A single estimate is drawn at random from the data and linear interpolation is used to extract the local value at each coastal grid point.	Two of the three global GIA estimates used in Palmer et al (2020) are used here. The first is based on the ICE-5G (VM2 L90) model (Peltier, 2004). The other is from the Australian National University based on an update of Nakada and Lambeck (1988) in 2004-2005 (Slangen et al., 2014).

3.4. Key findings

- The projections of GMSL rise produced by the ProFSea tool over the 21st century yield similar ranges to those presented in IPCC AR5 (Church et al., 2013).
- The single largest component of uncertainty is that associated with the updated Antarctic ice dynamics component following Levermann et al. (2014), resulting in a slightly higher central estimate for the RCP8.5 scenario compared to AR5.
- Palmer et al. (2020) provides local MSL projections for 16 global locations, rates of sea-level change under emissions scenario RCP2.6 are relatively stable, whereas under RCP8.5 sea-level rise will accelerate over the 21st century.
- The UKCP18 21st century projections of time-mean sea-level change around the UK vary substantially by climate change scenario and geographic location (Palmer et al., 2018), suggesting that the likelihood of UK coastal flooding is expected to increase over the 21st century and beyond under all RCP scenarios. This means that we can expect to see both an increase in the frequency and magnitude of extreme water levels around the UK coastline.
- In the longer term, Increased likelihood of future flooding will be dominated by the effects of time-mean sea-level rise, rather than changes in atmospheric storminess associated with extreme coastal sea level events (Howard et al., 2014).

4. Setting up the tool

4.1. Basic set-up

The GitHub repository is:

- <https://GitHub.com/MetOffice/ProFSea-tool.git>

The code base is written in Python 3.6. The code base makes use of a conda environment; this is provided in the `ProFSea-environment.yml` file. It is recommended that users create an environment from the `ProFSea-environment.yml` following:

```
conda env create --file ProFSea-environment.yml
conda activate ProFSea-environment
```

If using an IDEs (Integrated Development Environments) for Python programming, ensure this is appropriately linked to the above environment. Note it may take several hours for the conda environment to initially load and activate.

4.2. Data requirements

The ProFSea tool requires numerous datasets to run. Except for tide gauge data, these datasets are all published on CEDA and can be downloaded from:

- [Dataset Record: Met Office Projecting Future Sea Level \(ProFSea\) tool, input datasets \(ceda.ac.uk\)](https://ceda.ac.uk)

Each of these are discussed in more detail below.

4.2.1. Coupled Model Intercomparison Project data

Following IPCC AR5, the sea-level projections produced by the ProFSea tool make use of simulations of GMST (*tas*) and global thermosteric sea-level rise (*zostoga*) from 21 CMIP5 climate model simulations. The full list of CMIP5 models is:

- ACCESS1-0
- bcc-csm1-1
- CNRM-CM5
- CSIRO-Mk3-6-0
- CanESM2
- GFDL-ESM2G
- GFDL-ESM2M
- GISS-E2-R
- HadGEM2-CC
- HadGEM2-ES
- inmcm4
- IPSL-CM5A-LR
- IPSL-CM5A-MR
- MIROC-ESM
- MIROC-ESM-CHEM
- MIROC5
- MPI-ESM-LR
- MPI-ESM-MR
- MRI-CGCM3
- NorESM1-M
- NorESM1-ME

CMIP5 model experiment simulation data are stored on CEDA systems.

At regional scales, changes in ocean dynamic sea level (arising from changes in ocean circulation and/or density) are important determinants of local sea-level change. To account for this, the global thermosteric sea level (*zostoga*) and ocean dynamic sea level (*zos*) are drift-corrected using a linear fit to the corresponding pre-industrial control simulations.

The steric component of the sea-level projections is based on the regression slopes between local steric component of sea level (*zostoga* + *zos*) and global thermosteric sea level (*zostoga*). The function `calculate_sl_components`, called in `step3_process_regional_sealevel_projections.py` (see Section 5.3), reads in the calculated slope coefficients. For a non-UK location, the regression coefficient is drawn at random from across all CMIP5 models for each scenario.

For UK coastal locations, CMIP5 slope coefficients were previously developed for UKCP18 (Palmer et al., 2018). In the ProFSea tool, these regression coefficients are drawn at random from across all CMIP5 models and all UK coastal grid boxes for each scenario. The random draw is weighted so that there is an equal chance of drawing each CMIP5 model, irrespective of how many grid boxes they have adjacent to the UK coast. The UKCP18 CMIP5 slope coefficients are stored on CEDA systems.

Where a model has not been run for the RCP2.6 emissions scenario the RCP4.5 emissions scenario is used in its place. The RCP2.6 emissions scenario is unavailable in the following CMIP5 models:

- ACCESS1-0
- HadGEM2-CC
- Inmcm4

4.2.2. Glacial isostatic adjustment data

The sea-level projections account for the spatial patterns of sea-level change associated with glacial isostatic adjustment (GIA), i.e., the response of the Earth's mantle to the last deglaciation, including the effect of vertical land motion.

For UK locations the ProFSea tool uses the observationally constrained GIA estimates developed for the NERC BRITICE-CHRONO project (Sarah Bradley, pers. Comm.), following the same methodology as UKCP18. For locations outside the UK the ProFSea tool uses two global GIA estimates. The first is based on the ICE-5G (VM2 L90) model (Peltier, 2004). The other is from the Australian National University based on an update of Nakada and Lambeck (1988) in 2004-2005 (Slangen et al., 2014).

The differences between UK and non-UK locations are documented in Table 3-1.

4.2.3. Tide gauge data

It is a useful exercise to compare local sea-level projections to suitable tide gauge records. Users should be aware that the projections include the vertical land motion effects associated with GIA. As such, it may be most appropriate to compare against tide gauge records that have not been corrected for vertical land motions.

Tide gauge metadata and observations can be obtained from:

- [Permanent Service for Mean Sea Level \(PSMSL\)](#)

To run the ProFSea tool, all available tide gauge metadata and observations from PSMSL need to be downloaded by the user. Using the link above click on 'Data' from the landing page, then select the link to 'Download all Data', from here it is possible to download the 'RLR Annual' files. This will download a .zip file. The ProFSea tool requires the following files:

- Filelist.txt (contains the station ID, latitude, longitude and station name)
- Over 2000 ID.rlrdata files (for each of the stations in the filelist.txt, this contains the quality assured annual mean sea level observations)

4.3. Projection baseline period

Sea-level projections are usually expressed relative to the average of a defined period (the baseline period). The GMSL Monte Carlo discussed in Section 3.1.1, uses a 1986-2005 baseline (Church et al., 2013 and Palmer et al., 2020).

The 21st century projections produced as part of UKCP18 use a baseline of 1981-2000 whereby a small adjustment is applied to the component timeseries (Palmer et al., 2018). This is based on the average difference between the two baseline periods, calculated using reconstructions of GMSL from four tide-gauges. The result is an offset of +0.011m for the total sea level, which is then applied across each component according to their relative size in the sea-level budget.

4.4. CMIP Sea

Some of the CMIP5 climate models on their native grids, do not represent physical connections between oceans which are separated by a narrow stretch of water, these are termed “detached marginal seas” (e.g., the Mediterranean, Hudson Bay, Baltic Sea, etc.). Essentially, this means that ocean processes in the detached marginal sea are not well represented; the sea surface height behaves differently compared to the nearby ocean. The user is required to specify if the location they are generating sea-level projections for is within a detached marginal sea, if so, the user should update the `cmip_sea` variable in the `user-settings.yml` (see Section 4.5).

Within detached marginal seas, some of the CMIP5 climate models have significant numerical instabilities, while others project a different sea surface height evolution. The ProFSea tool uses the same methodology as the IPCC AR5 (Church et al., 2013) to remove these errors and to treat all the models consistently - models are excluded from the analysis if the detached marginal sea was disconnected from the adjacent ocean basin, on the common $1^\circ \times 1^\circ$ grid.

The following is a list of all available CMIP climate models that IPCC AR5 state are appropriate for use in detached marginal seas:

- bcc-csm1-1
- CanESM2
- GFDL-ESM2M
- HadGEM2-CC
- HadGEM2-ES
- MIROC-ESM
- MIROC-ESM-CHEM
- MIROC5

Note that sea-level projections may still show evidence of numerical instabilities and results in these areas should be used with caution, if at all.

4.5. User Inputs

Several inputs are required to run the ProFSea tool, these are defined in the `user-settings.yml` file and described in Table 4-1.

The `user-settings.yml` in the GitHub repository is configured for Port Stanley, Falklands. To run the tool for a different location the commands need to be changed as described.

Table 4-1: Summary of user inputs required to run the ProFSea tool. Each of these inputs will need setting by the user in the user-settings.yml.

User Input	Command	Example	Description
Region of the world	siteinfo: region:	'Falkland_example'	Appended to the output directory, to create the final folder structure.
Tide gauge name or site name	siteinfo: sitename:	['Stanley II']	If using a tide gauge from PSMSL ensure the spelling is the same as that recorded in the filelist.txt to ensure correct latitude and longitude are retrieved by the tool. If using a site name, latitude and longitude need to be specified. It is not possible to leave this empty.
Latitude and longitude	siteinfo: sitelaton:	[[[]] [[-33.0964, 27.9911]]	If using a tide gauge name from PSMSL leave empty. If using a site name (i.e. a location not in PSMSL), specify a latitude longitude pair. This should be specified in decimal degrees where north (south) of the equator is positive (negative), and east (west) of the meridian is positive (negative).
Output directory	baseoutdir:	'/home/user/sl_output/'	The base directory of where you want the output to be saved. As above, note that the region of the world will be appended.
Scientific method	sciencemethod:	'global' 'UK'	The scientific method is used to identify if sea-level projections follow the methodology set out by Palmer et al. (2020), or UKCP18 (Palmer et al. 2018).
Tide gauge information data source	tidegaugeinfo: source:	PSMSL	Default option.
Tide gauge information temporal scale	tidegaugeinfo: datafq:	['annual']	Default option.
Directory for PSMSL tide gauge information	tidegaugeinfo: psmsldir:	'/home/user/data/PSMSL/'	Location of downloaded PSMSL tide gauge information (filelist.txt and ID.rlrdata).
CMIP5 models sub-selection	cmipinfo: cmip_sea:	'all' 'marginal'	An option to use all available CMIP5 models or to use a sub-selection of CMIP5 models identified in AR5 specifically for 'detached marginal seas' as discussed in Section 4.4.

Base directory for CMIP zos and zostoga data	sealevelbasedir:	'/deposited2023/profsea_to ol/cmip5/'	Directory for the CMIP zos and zostoga data, downloaded from CEDA.
Directory for UKCP18 CMIP5 slope coefficients	slopecoeffsuk:	'/deposited2023/profsea_to ol/uk_cmip_slope_coefficients/'	Directory for the CMIP5 slope coefficients developed for UKCP18, downloaded from CEDA.
Global GIA estimates (Lambeck, ICE5G)	giaestimates: global:	'/deposited2023/profsea_to ol/gia_estimates /global_GIA_interpolators.pickle'	Directory and filename of the GIA estimates to be used within the global set-up of the ProFSea tool, downloaded from CEDA.
UK GIA estimates (UK specific estimates)	giaestimates: uk:	'/deposited2023/profsea_to ol/gia_estimates/Bradley_GIA_interpolator.pickle'	Directory and filename of the gia estimates to be used within UK set-up of the ProFSea tool, downloaded from CEDA.
Gravity, rotation and solid-Earth deformation (GRD) fingerprints	fingerprints: slangendir: fingerprints: spadadir: fingerprints: klemanndir:	'/deposited2023/profsea_to ol/grd_fingerprints/' '/deposited2023/profsea_to ol/grd_fingerprints/' '/deposited2023/profsea_to ol/grd_fingerprints/'	Directory of the GRD fingerprints, downloaded from CEDA. These are stored in the same location on CEDA, but the filepath in the tool needs specifying for each fingerprint. It is possible for the user to download this data into different directories.
Monte Carlo timeseries	montecarloDir:	'/deposited2023/profsea_to ol/monte_carlo_timeseries/'	Directory of Monte Carlo time series for new projections, downloaded from CEDA.

5. Running the tool

The tool comprises four steps, outlined in Sections 5.1 – 5.4 below.

It is recommended when first running the tool to use the default settings in the `user-settings.yml` (note you will need to update the input and output directories depending on where your data is stored). The output can be checked against the data and figures stored in the repository. Once satisfied you can replicate the results, you can then run the tool for a location of your choice by altering the arguments in the `user-settings.yml` per Table 4-1.

Note that for a non-UK location users must run the tool from Step 1 (see Section 0), however as regression relationships have already been developed for UK locations (per UKCP18), it is possible to start the tool at Step 3 (see Section 5.3). Each script needs running in turn by executing the python script. Table A 1 summarises the outputs of each step in the ProFSea tool.

5.1. Step 1 - Extract CMIP

Script: `step1_extract_cmip.py`

Note if running projections for the UK the user should start at step 3.

5.1.1. Overview

This script loops through the global climate models to find the nearest grid box in the CMIP models to the user defined site. This is completed by iteratively checking the CMIP grid boxes surrounding the site location. Users are required to visually inspect the outputs to make sure suitable grid boxes have been allocated for the site(s) in question.

In the first instance to check if there is a grid box immediately covering the site location, if not the code will loop through all the grid boxes one grid box removed from the site, and if none of these are accepted by the user the code will loop through all grid boxes two boxes removed from the site and so on until an acceptable grid box is found.

Figure 5-1 shows an example map for Port Stanley, Falkland Islands. The site location is represented as the red cross and the closest CMIP grid box accepted by the user is the black circle, the code base will ask the user if the selected CMIP box is appropriate, the user will need to close the pop-up map and write 'Y' or 'N' into the interactive window. If the user writes 'N' the code base will continue looping through grid boxes until the one shown is accepted by the user.

Caution is required here as the current code base does not allow a user to revert to the previous grid box. The site is defined in the `user-settings.yml` file in one of two different

ways as described in Table 4-1.

Figure 5-1: Example map for Port Stanley, Falkland Islands, showing the sea surface height (SSH) from the bcc-csm1-1 model. Site location is represented as the red cross and the closest CMIP grid box, is represented by the black circle.

5.1.2. Outputs

For each CMIP model, a map is produced of the sea surface height above the geoid in meters, re-gridded onto a 1x1 degree latitude-longitude grid, identifying the latitude and longitude of the site location as well as the associated user selected grid box (Figure 5-1). Note the map is shown iteratively until the user accepts a grid box, 'Y', and only the final map is saved as an output.

A single corresponding .csv file is produced. The .csv file contains the site name, site latitude, site longitude and the corresponding latitude and longitude grid box boundaries of each CMIP models (black dot in map showing the accepted grid box). These are read in and used by the next step of the tool.

5.2. Step 2 - Extract global local regression

Script: `step2_extract_steric_dyn_regression.py`

5.2.1. Overview

The second script calculates the regression slopes between the local stericodynamic

component of sea level ($zostoga + zos$) and the global thermosteric sea level ($zostoga$) for the period 2005-2100 and 2050-2100. The local sterodynamic and global thermosteric sea-level change should be similar, if they aren't, then either the local change is increasing faster or slower than the global average.

5.2.2. Outputs

For each CMIP model, a scatter graph is produced of the local sterodynamic component of sea level (labelled, local sea level) and global thermosteric sea level (labelled, global thermal expansion) for the available RCPs emission scenarios – RCP2.6, RCP4.5 and RCP8.5. All graphs are based on 2005-2100 projections. An example of this is shown in Figure 5-2.

A single corresponding .csv file is produced. The .csv file contains the information as calculated in step 1 along with the regression slopes for the periods 2005-2100 ($slope_{05_00}$) and 2050-2100 ($slope_{50_00}$), for each CMIP model and each RCP scenario. Where a model has not been run for the RCP2.6 emissions scenario this is documented as 'NA', in the following step the RCP4.5 emissions scenario is used in its place.

Figure 5-2: Example graph for Port Stanley, Falkland Islands of regression relationship for the bcc-csm1-1 model between local sea level and global thermal expansion, for the period 2005-2100. Relationships are plotted for all available emission scenarios: RCP2.6 (blue); RCP4.5 (cyan); and RCP8.5 (red). For comparison, the dotted line shows the 1:1 relationship.

5.3. Step 3 - Process sea-level projections

Script: `step_3 _process_regional_sealevel_projections.py`

5.3.1. Overview

Script three calculates the global sea-level projections and local sea-level projections at a given site, following the Monte Carlo procedure, which is shown schematically in Figure 3-2, based on the different contributing factors. Note a small adjustment is applied to the component timeseries for UK projections, as discussed in Section 4.3.

Thermal expansion

The local steric component of the sea-level projections is based on the regression slopes between the local steric sea level and global thermosteric sea level.

For a non-UK location, the regression slopes are calculated by the tool, as discussed in Section 5.2. In this case, the regression coefficient is drawn at random from across all CMIP5 models for each scenario. Where a model has not been run for the RCP2.6 emissions scenario then the RCP4.5 emissions scenario is used.

For a location in the UK, CMIP5 slope coefficients were previously developed for UKCP18 (Palmer et al., 2018). In this case, the regression coefficient is drawn at random from across all 21 CMIP5 climate model simulations and all UK coastal grid boxes for each scenario. The random draw is weighted so that there is an equal chance of drawing each CMIP5 model, irrespective of how many grid boxes they have adjacent to the UK coast. These slope coefficients are stored in a file, as described in Table 4-1, therefore it is possible to start from this step for a UK location.

To distinguish between global and UKCP18 slope coefficients the user defined variable, `sciencemethod` needs to be specified, as described in Table 4-1.

Mass addition timeseries

The mass addition timeseries (glaciers, ice sheets and land water) are then combined with their corresponding fingerprints at the specified latitude and longitude, discussed in Section 3.2. This selection is made at random, but the same model is used for all fingerprints to preserve any correlated errors.

Glacial Isostatic Adjustment

Local sea-level projections have an additional component from GIA which does not apply to the global components. UK specific GIA estimates were developed as part of UKCP18 and used in the ProFSea tool for UK locations, elsewhere the GIA estimates are based on Lambeck and ICE5G; discussed briefly in Section 3.2.

The GIA estimates are read in from data files, based on the user defined variable `sciencemethod`, as described in Table 4-1.

5.3.2. Outputs

Global-mean sea-level projections are generated by the tool and saved in a file, following the format:

- LOCATION_scenario_projection_2100_global.csv

Regional sea-level projections are also generated by the tool and saved in a file following the format:

- LOCATION_scenario_projection_2100_regional.csv

Both of these files contain sea-level projections for the sum total and component parts following the format:

- Total sea-level change: sum
- Thermal expansion: exp
- Antarctic ice dynamics: antdyn
- Antarctic surface mass balance: antsemb
- Total contribution from Antarctica: antnet
- Greenland ice dynamics: greendyn
- Greenland surface mass balance: greensmb
- Total contribution from Greenland: greennet
- Worldwide glaciers: glacier
- Changes in landwater storage: landwater

All the sea-level projections generated by the ProFSea tool are provided for 2007-2100 for the three future emissions scenarios (RCP2.6, RCP4.5 and RCP8.5) and are available for nine percentiles (5th, 10th, 30th, 33rd, 50th, 67th, 70th, 90th and 95th), the projections are given in meters.

5.4. Step 4 - Plot local sea level components

Script: `step4_plot_regional_sea_level.py`

5.4.1. Overview

The final script reads in the local sea-level projections at a given site and uses these to create a number of graphs. It is a useful exercise to compare the global sea-level projections produced by the ProFSea tool to those produced in IPCC AR5. Having read in the local sea-level projections, the ProFSea tool also reads in the IPCC AR5 global sea-level projections and produces a graph so the user can compare the projections, an example for Port Stanley, Falkland Islands is shown in Figure 5-3.

Another useful exercise is to compare local sea-level projections to nearby tide gauge records.

The annual mean sea level observations from PSMSL are read in from the nearest tide gauge. If the user defined site location is the tide gauge name, the annual mean sea level observations are read in for this tide gauge. If the user defined site location is based on latitude and longitude, the ProFSea tool calculates the closest tide gauge to the site based on the Haversine formula and reads in the annual mean sea level observations. An example for Port Stanley, Falkland Islands is shown in Figure 5-4.

Examples of the other graphs produced by the ProFSea tool can be found in the supplementary material.

Figure 5-3: Comparison of the global-mean sea-level projections produced by the ProFSea tool and those presented in the IPCC AR5 (left panel; Church et al, 2013). Also shown are the local sea-level projections for Port Stanley, Falkland Islands compared to the global-mean (right panel). Bold lines indicate the central estimate with the range (5th-95th percentile) indicated by the shaded region or dotted lines according to the figure legend. All projections are shown relative to a 1986-2005 baseline period. Note one graph produced per RCP scenario requested.

Figure 5-4: Local sea-level projections for Port Stanley, Falkland Islands and annual mean sea level observations from Stanley II tide gauge to illustrate the observed sea level variability. The timeseries are plotted relative to a baseline period of 1981-2000. Coloured lines indicate the central estimates according to the figure legend. Shaded regions represent the projection range (5th-95th percentile) for the corresponding RCP scenario as indicated in the legend.

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Supplementary Material

Figure A 1: Changes in the amount of land-based ice and water storage induce spatial patterns of local MSL change as a result of changes to the Earth's gravity, rotation, and solid-Earth deformation. Gregory et al. (2019) refers to these effects collectively as GRD (Gravity, Rotation, Deformation fingerprints). Each of the sea level "mass fingerprints" for the UK region associated with changes in land ice mass and water changes are shown, as per individual titles, updated from Slangen et al. (2014). Fingerprints represent the proportion of sea-level change that is experienced locally for a unit increase in global sea level (no units). Reproduced from: UKCP18 Marine Report (Palmer et al., 2018).

Figure A 2: left) The mean of 15 estimates of the ongoing regional relative sea-level change associated with glacial isostatic adjustment (GIA), in mm/yr, right) the associated 90% confidence interval, assuming a normal distribution, in mm/ yr. Data provided from the NERC BRITICE_CHRONO project (Sarah Bradley, pers. comm.). Reproduced from: UKCP18 Marine Report (Palmer et al., 2018).

Python script number	.csv file(s) description	.csv naming convention	.png(s) description	.png naming convention
1	One .csv file - contains the site name, site latitude, site longitude and the CMIP models' grid box coordinates along with the corresponding latitude and longitude of the user accepted grid box.	LOCATION_ij_1x1_coords.csv	A map per CMIP5 model - of the sea surface height (SSH) from the model, site location (red cross) and the user accepted grid box (black circle).	LOCATION_model_name_ij_figure.png
2	One .csv file - contains the CMIP models' grid box coordinates along with the corresponding latitude and longitude (per step 1) and the regression slopes for the periods 2005-2100 (slope_05_00) and 2050-2100 (slope_50_00), for each CMIP model and each RCP scenario.	LOCATION_zos_regression.csv	A scatter graph per CMIP5 model - scatter graph of the local sterodynamic component of sea level and global thermosteric sea level for the available RCP emission scenarios. Based on 2005-2100 projection only.	LOCATION_zos_regression_2005-2100.png
3	For each RCP two .csv files – one contains global-mean sea-level projections and one contains regional sea-level projections. Both contain the sum total and component parts.	LOCATION_scenario_projection_2100_global.csv LOCATION_scenario_projection_2100_regional.csv	NA	NA
4	NA	NA	7 figures (per report and supplementary)	01_LOCATION.png

Table A 1: Overview of outputs produced by each step of the ProFSea tool

Figure A 3: Local sea-level projections for Port Stanley, Falkland Islands. The timeseries are plotted relative to a baseline period of 1986-2005. Coloured lines indicate the central estimates according to the figure legend. Shaded regions represent the projection range (5th-95th percentile) for the corresponding RCP scenario (left panel) or sea level component (right panel).

Figure A 4: Local sea-level projections for Port Stanley, Falkland Island. Solid lines indicate the central estimate (50th percentile) and dashed lines indicate the range (5th-95th percentile) for each RCP as indicated in the legend. All projections are presented relative to a baseline period of 1986-2005.

Figure A 5: Comparison between the global sea-level projections and local sea-level projections for Port Stanley, Falkland Islands produced by the tool, where left panel is RCP2.6, middle panel is RCP4.5 and right panel is RCP8.5. The global-mean sea-level projections central estimate (50th percentile) is represented as the bold dashed black line, with the corresponding uncertainty range (5th-95th percentile) represented as the dotted black lines. The local sea-level projections (total) central estimate (50th percentile) is represented as the bold black line, with the corresponding uncertainty range (5th-95th percentile) represented as the grey shaded region. Also shown is the central estimate and uncertainty range for the local thermal expansion (denoted Ocean in the legend) component of sea-level projections along with all other components as indicated in the legend. All projections are shown relative to a 1981-2000 baseline period.

Figure A 6: Comparison between the global sea-level projections presented in the IPCC AR5 (Church et al., 2013) and local sea-level projections for Port Stanley, Falkland Islands produced by the tool, where left panel is RCP2.6, middle panel is RCP4.5 and right panel is RCP8.5. The global-mean sea-level projections central estimate (50th percentile) is represented as the bold dashed black line, with the corresponding uncertainty range (5th-95th percentile) represented as the dotted black lines. The local sea-level projections (total) central estimate (50th percentile) is represented as the bold black line, with the corresponding uncertainty range (5th-95th percentile) represented as the grey shaded region. Also shown is the central estimate and uncertainty range for the local thermal expansion (denoted Ocean in the legend) component of sea-level projections along with all other components as indicated in the legend. All projections are shown relative to a 1981-2000 baseline period.

Figure A 7: Components of sea-level projections for Port Stanley, Falkland Islands under emissions scenario RCP8.5. The horizontal lines indicate the central estimate and shaded regions indicate the range (5th-95th percentile) for each sea level component. The sea-level projections are relative to a baseline period of 1981-2000. Note only one graph produced for RCP8.5.

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